

Modelling of Nonlinear Problem Masstransfer in Three-Layer System

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 28 October 2021 Corresponding Author: Rustam Karjavovich Berdiev	This article discusses modeling of nonlinear system of the differential equations in private derivatives of parabolic type. Especially, modelling of nonlinear problem masstransfer in three-layer system will be analyzed in details.
KEYWORDS: Modeling Of Nonlinear System, Parabolic Type, Masstransfer	

INTRODUCTION

We proceed from the following nonlinear system of differential equations

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varepsilon(t) - w_0 \left(1 - \frac{m_\varepsilon - y}{m_\varepsilon - y_{kp}} \right) + \frac{k_1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 y^2}{\partial x^2} &= \mu_1 \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} + k_2 \frac{y - h}{m_2} \\ \frac{T}{a} \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} &= T \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x^2} + T\chi(H - h) + \frac{k_2}{m_2} (y - h) \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (1)$$

Where $w_0, m_\varepsilon, y_{kp}, k_1, k_2, m_2, \mu_1, a, T, \chi, H$ - some positive constants; $\varepsilon(t)$ - continuous differentiable function ; t ; $y(x, t), h(x, t)$ - the desired functions. Introducing notation

$$a_1 = \frac{w_0 y_{kp}}{m_\varepsilon - y_{kp}}; \quad b_1 = \frac{a_1}{y_{kp}}; \quad \mu_2 = \frac{k_2}{m_2}; \quad \mu_3 = \frac{T}{a};$$

The main results and findings

We will rewrite the system (1) in the form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu_1 \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} &= \frac{k_1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 y^2}{\partial x^2} - \mu_2 (y - h) + a_1 - b_1 y + \varepsilon(t) \\ \mu_3 \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} &= T \frac{\partial^2 h}{\partial x^2} + T\chi(H - h) + \mu_2 (y - h) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

are looking for the solution of system (2) in the form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y(x, t) &= \alpha(t)(L - x)^2 + \beta(t) \\ h(x, t) &= \varphi(t)(L - x)^2 + \psi(t) \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (3)$$

Where $\alpha(t), \beta(t), \varphi(t)$ и $\psi(t)$ – doubly differentiable functions to be defined. In this case, system (3) automatically satisfies the conditions

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=L} = \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=L} = 0$$

From (3) we find

$$y^2(x, t) = \alpha^2(t)(L - x)^4 + 2\alpha(t)\beta(t)(l - x)^2 + \beta^2(t);$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 y^2}{\partial x^2} = 12\alpha^2(t)(L - x)^2 + 4\alpha(t)\beta(t) \tag{4}$$

Substituting (3) into (2) taking into account (4) we get

$$\mu_1 \left[\dot{\alpha}(L - x)^2 + \dot{\beta} \right] = 6k_1\alpha^2(t)(L - x)^2 + 2k_1\alpha(t)\beta(t) + a_1 - b_1[\alpha(t)(L - x)^2 + \beta(t)] + \varepsilon(t) - \mu_2[\alpha(t) - \varphi(t)](L - x)^2 - \mu_2[\beta(t) - \psi(t)];$$

$$\mu_3 \left[\dot{\varphi}(L - x)^2 + \dot{\psi} \right] = 2T\varphi(t) + T\chi H - T\chi\varphi(t)(L - x)^2 - T\chi\psi(t) + \mu_2[\alpha(t) - \varphi(t)](L - x)^2 + \mu_2[\beta(t) - \psi(t)].$$

Equating the coefficients at $(L - x)^2$ and coefficients independent of $(L - x)^2$, we obtain the following nonlinear system of ordinary differential equations

$$\mu_1 \dot{\alpha} = 6k_1\alpha^2(t) - b_1\alpha(t) - \mu_2[\alpha(t) - \varphi(t)]; \tag{5}$$

$$\mu_1 \dot{\beta} = 2k_1\alpha(t)\beta(t) + a_1 - b_1\beta(t) + \varepsilon(t) - \mu_2[\beta(t) - \psi(t)]; \tag{6}$$

$$\mu_3 \dot{\varphi} = -T\chi\varphi(t) + \mu_2[\alpha(t) - \varphi(t)]; \tag{7}$$

$$\mu_3 \dot{\psi} = 2T\varphi(t) + T\chi H - T\chi\psi(t) + \mu_2[\beta(t) - \psi(t)]. \tag{8}$$

From equation (5) we find

$$\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{\mu_2} \left(\mu_1 \dot{\alpha} + b_1\alpha - 6k_1\alpha^2 \right) + \alpha = \frac{1}{\mu_2} \left(\mu_1 \dot{\alpha} + 6k_1\alpha^2 \right) + \frac{b_1 + \mu_2}{\mu_2} \alpha \tag{9}$$

From where follows

$$\dot{\varphi}(t) = \frac{1}{\mu_2} \left[\mu_1 \ddot{\alpha} - 12k_1\alpha\dot{\alpha} + (b_1 + \mu_2)\dot{\alpha} \right] \tag{10}$$

Relations (9) and (10) are substituted in (7)

$$\frac{\mu_3}{\mu_2} \left[\mu_1 \ddot{\alpha} - 12k_1\alpha\dot{\alpha} + (b_1 + \mu_2)\dot{\alpha} \right] = -\frac{T\chi}{\mu_2} \left[\mu_1 \dot{\alpha} - 6k_1\alpha^2 + (b_1 + \mu_2)\alpha \right] - \mu_1 \dot{\alpha} - b_1\alpha + 6k_1\alpha^2.$$

After the reduction of such, we come to the equation

$$\frac{\mu_1\mu_3}{\mu_2} \ddot{\alpha} - \frac{12k_1\mu_3}{\mu_2} \alpha\dot{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\mu_2} [\mu_3(b_1 + \mu_2) + \mu_1T\chi + \mu_1\mu_2] \dot{\alpha} - \frac{6k_1}{\mu_2} (\mu_2 + T\chi)\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{\mu_2} [b_1\mu_2 + (b_1 + \mu_2)T\chi] \alpha = 0,$$

or abbreviating to μ_2 , we get

$$\mu_1\mu_3 \ddot{\alpha} - 12k_1\mu_3\alpha\dot{\alpha} + [\mu_3(b_1 + \mu_2) + \mu_1T\chi + \mu_1\mu_2] \dot{\alpha} - 6k_1(\mu_2 + T\chi)\alpha^2 +$$

$$+ [b_1\mu_2 + (b_1 + \mu_2)I\chi]\alpha = 0 \tag{11}$$

Regarding the function $h(x, t)$ let's introduce an additional condition

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=0} = \varpi(t), \tag{12}$$

where $\varpi(t)$ – a known doubly differentiable function of t , then it follows from the second equation of system (3) that

$$\varphi(t) = -\frac{1}{L}\varpi(t) \tag{13}$$

As a result, the general Riccati equation follows from (9)

$$\dot{\alpha} = A_1\alpha^2 - A_2\alpha + \lambda(t) \tag{14}$$

By staging $\alpha = E(t)u(t)$, где $E(t) = \exp \int (-A_2)dt$

leads equation (14) to the form

$$\dot{u} = A_1e^{-A_2t}u^2 + \lambda(t)e^{A_2t}, \text{ т.е.} \tag{15}$$

the linear term vanishes. By asking $\varpi(t)$, and therefore and $\lambda(t)$ decision $u(t)$ you can write out [1] and write on the basis of (11) the following equation

$$\ddot{\alpha} - 12\frac{k_1}{\mu_1}\alpha\dot{\alpha} + B_1\dot{\alpha} - 6\frac{k_1}{\mu_1\mu_3}\alpha^2 = A_3\zeta(t), \tag{16}$$

which, when substituting solution (14), turns into an identity.

We are interested in an independent solution with a possible change in the right part (16)

Conclusion

In [1] the method of obtaining the solution of equation f. 6.37 is specified (p.490)

$$y'' + 2yy' + f(x)(y' + y^2) = g(x) \text{ using substitution}$$

$$v(x) = y' + y^2, \text{ which boils down to } v' + f(x)v = g(x). \tag{17}$$

In our case, it is necessary to use the substitution

$$w(t) = \alpha' - \frac{6k_1}{\mu_1\mu_3B} \text{ and counting the variations of the left honor constant (16) of consciousness alignment to (17).}$$

Functions $\beta(t)$ and $\psi(t)$ are found by integrating (6) and (8).

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